

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ

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НОМЕР-1**

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Телефон номер: +99894-410 11 55, **E-mail:** tahririyat@imfaktor.uz

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URINOVA Urazgul

English teacher at Transport Academic Lyceum

GENRE IN ACADEMIC PROSE AND WHAT MAKES DIFFERENT FROM OTHER VARIETIES

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ANNOTASIYA: Ushbu maqolada janr tushunchasi, talabalarning ilmiy uslubda turli janrlardan foydalanilishi va tilni o'qitish jarayonida uning qo'llanilishi yoritib berilgan va sohadagi yetuk olimlarning bu mavzuga oid fikr-mulohazalari o'rganilgan. Shuningdek, ilgari surilgan g'oyalarni nazariy jihatdan chuqur tahlil qilish, ilmiy uslubda janrning boshqalardan farqli xususiyatlarini umumlashtirish va ularni tanqidiy baholashga oid fikrlar ham aks etgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ilmiy uslub, janr, ESP, shaxsi noma'lumlik, AW, akademik soha, struktura, janrning muhimligi, ideologiya.

АННОТАЦИЯ: В данной статье освещается понятие жанра, использование учащимися различных жанров в научном методе и его использование в процессе обучения языку, а также исследуются мнения передовых ученых в данной области по данной теме. Также отражены мысли, связанные с теоретическим углубленным анализом выдвинутых идей, обобщением в научном методе отличных от других особенностей жанра и их критической оценкой.

Ключевые слова: научный метод, жанр, ESP, личная анонимность, AW, академическое поле, структура, значимость жанра, идеология.

In recent years, a growing attention has been given to the conception of genre and its usage in language teaching learning. Students are typically required to write and submit based on different kinds of genres in their academic writing. The main objective of this study is to analyze the sources related to the topic and examine the information critically by evaluating and synthesizing. Although it includes a variety of different theories by many authors, this review will focus on these recurring major themes, which emerge frequently throughout the literature review. They are common aspects of genres in academic prose including relationship between genres and community, impersonality and the importance of genres in application. Some contradictory views are also covered.

Defining the connection of genres with the community

Genres are closely correlated with society according to different fields. They can vary depending on different disciplines. Geertz's (1973) asserts, "Knowledge and academic writing depend on the actions of members of local communities. Community, in fact, helps us not only interpret and understand genre use better but also to explain genre variation across different groups" (p. 548). Likewise, Bazerman (1994) states that "genres are forms of life, ways of being, and frames for social action and they should be considered what people, as groups and individuals, recognize them to be..." (p. 92). Swales, Sheldon Smith who is an EAP instructor and Faigley, Bakhtin, Eunsook Shim also give similar points of view regarding this. According to Sheldon Smith (2009) , "genres can be considered as social actions intended for a specific audience, a specific purpose and context" (p. 7). This is primarily because genres are distinguished based on the level of education, particular activities and various disciplines. Even in the same sphere, genres may vary depending on the same dimensions. For instance, there is some discrepancy between a paper of literary criticism and a paper in literary history. However, they share some set of communicative aims. Before I introduced with this group presentation topic, I had read the article of Bay about the procedure of each genre and thought that genres were based on a rigid, fixed structure and a rigid criteria, which we had to follow mechanically. That said, after exploring the topic deeply I have changed my mind and realized that genres are a style of writing and speaking which is aimed at enabling people to communicate, work together and integrate. When it comes to content, style, objective and organization, in academic writing genres show similar peculiarities. More importantly, a genre can be adapted and converted according to the new context or audience. Eunsook Shim supports this view and contends that "New ways of looking at genre have emerged in the field of teaching English for Specific Purposes (ESP). Genre is viewed not as a tool for classifying texts types but as a dynamic activity in social contexts. The key characteristic feature of a genre is communicative purpose" (p. 400). Overall, in academic writing genres can be interpreted only from the perspective of a society instead of an individual point of view.

The special feature of academic writing

Obviously, the usage of impersonality is highlighted in academic writing, which is a different feature from nonacademic writing since it is a formal mode of writing whose target audience is predominantly a scholarly audience. They are based on solid evidence, well-researched examples, justification and highly investigated data. Kuhn (1962) suggests that "The conventions of impersonality in science articles thus play an important role in reinforcing an objective ideology by portraying the legitimacy of hard science knowledge as built on socially invariant criteria" (p. 553). On the contrary, Hyland (2001) argues that "Another important feature of research writing is the writer's reference to self: how far they want to personally intrude into their texts though use of 'I' or 'we', or use impersonal forms. Presenting a discursal self is central to the writing process, and we can't avoid projecting an impression of ourselves and how we stand in relation to our arguments, discipline, and readers" (p. 554). This information caught my attention and gave me a fresh, different perspective about impersonality. According to Dominador L. Pagliawan (2017), "In feature articles, these personal pronouns are allowed, especially if the author is narrating a personal experience, or featuring a place or event that he/she personally witnessed" (p. 39). He also provided a personal experience in the introduction part of his research paper.

However, Ivanic (1998) claims that “As to what extent new writing styles could apply is still a subject for debate. For sure, no new limits have already been drawn. Academic writers can still experiment on this, mostly consciously or at will” (p. 36). Based on my understanding, the usage of personal pronouns are acceptable in academic writing. For the existence of personalization can make research paper can make more authentic, credible and show a sense of responsibility from the author’s own confession, which makes different from other writers. But there is little consensus among researchers about the application of it in academic writing.

The importance of genres in academic field

All the sources that I read emphasize the significance of genres for not only students’ academic life, but also for those work in other scholar fields. The ability to use genres in academic writing (AW) can enable students facilitate the acquisition of writing skills and achieve particular writing outcomes in their academic performance. This can empower students to analyze various kinds of reading articles, reflect on the writing features of language and it also helps teachers to clarify what kind of texts that learners have to write in their target contexts and devise curriculum materials so as to meet the needs of students and enhance literacy skills acquired over years at a more advanced level expression. Ken Hyland (2008) states that “By becoming researchers of the specific genres our students will need in their fields of study we can help them understand the reasons for language choices and scaffold their effective use of them” (p. 561). Other authors also advocate this view that understanding genre writing can enable students to take part in academic disciplines and interact with professional specialists efficiently in the community. Hence, from my point of view, it is crucial that students should have a deeper understanding of genres in academic writing. Because knowing how to structure and examine texts in practice depending on the genre purpose is kind of a complicated process for learners. To confirm my view, there is an example in one of sources. In that research paper an experiment among Brazilian and Anglo-American students was conducted based on both qualitative and quantitative analysis. According to Antonio Dilamar (2012), “By becoming researchers of the specific genres our students will need in their fields of study we can help them understand the reasons for language choices and scaffold their effective use of them” (p. 331). That is why; understanding different genres of academic writing is of paramount importance in a real academic environment.

Identifying the paradoxical views

Having said that, I have found some conflicting ideas about genres as research tools. Swales (1990) asserts, “The research article was chosen as a genre because the research paper genre is the most common genre written in academic discourse” (p. 175). The validity of the data is flawed because in the other article Ken Hyland (2008) gives his opposite point of view about it and argues “I get the impression that teachers often see genre as a research tool but this is a misconception. Genre is actually a robust pedagogical approach perfectly suited to the teaching of academic writing in many contexts as it serves a key instructional purpose” (p. 1). To my way of thinking, more survey ought to be carried out about this disagreement.

Illustrating the problem

The primary problem of most sources is that they do not explore all aspects and types of academic writing genres because our group topic is a broad theme. Therefore, research articles cannot cover all features of genres and explain each of them in detail. For me, they seem to be somewhat incomplete.

But Sheldon Smith's full book called "Academic Writing genres" provides an in-depth explanation about genres and their distinguishing features and gives well-developed, accurate models by using suitable tables, charts, graphic and visual materials. His book is divided into chapters and sections and the focal purpose of the author is to explain every type of genres deeply. Other authors including Charles, B, Bay and Hasa do not entail precise and well-researched explanation based on past research, survey samples, observations and experiments conducted by scholars and linguistics. The data shown in their articles seem to be faulty because I have found out that main ideas can be seen repeatedly and examples are straightforward and do not comprise accurate evidence and justification in order to elucidate the genres in a detailed way and support the key ideas. Substantially, reading only research articles are not enough to comprehend the whole topic thoroughly apart from the book mentioned above because our topic is a wide theme and worth exploring.

Conclusion

In summary, it can be referred that genres are categorized according to specific contexts, disciplines and the level of education and how to organize writing structure is closely associated with genres. In each of genres, academic writing skills are required and applying them in a practical way are determined by particular aspects including impersonality. Although standard style and fixed rules are prerequisites for both academic and scholarly papers, they can be adjusted depending on the particular group of people or society in terms of its communicative purpose. The ability to use genres is of paramount importance as both students and those whose major is related to academic sphere. Especially, students typically encounter different kinds of genres. However, there are contradictory view regarding whether a research paper is regarded as a genre or not. Despite the fact that the majority of sources do not cover detailed data about each type of genres in academic prose, I have gained new insights and explored the topic in a theoretical way based on my perspective.

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